

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

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DEVELOPING AND IMPLEMENTING
A STANDARDIZED TRIAGE MODEL IN OB TRIAGE

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

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By

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ABSTRACT

Although the obstetric (OB) triage unit's primary function is to identify and treat high acuity and life-threatening events, inconsistency exists in clinical practice. The current first come first serve triage process limits the ability to care for urgent or emergent healthcare needs on time, and often creates an overcrowded triage unit. Overcrowding can result in delayed services, which, in turn, can cause the triage area to be further crowded. The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice project was to optimize patient safety and throughput efficiency by implementing a standardized triage model in OB triage. The aims of this project were to improve the accuracy of OB triage assessment and treatment, to improve the patient outcomes, and to decrease the length of stay in an OB triage. The PARIHS model was applied, translating evidence into practice. Using descriptive statistics, 150 available medical records were reviewed. The findings showed that the accuracy rate of the registered nurse (RN)'s initial assessment was acceptable at 85.3%. Three main chief complaints related to under-triage included preterm labor, decreased fetal movement, and falls. The RN's assessment time was reduced from 22 minutes to 5 minutes. No adverse patient outcomes nor improper patient discharge occurred due to inaccurate or delayed triage services. Patient safety was enhanced as resulted in a high rate of accuracy in triage acuity and the time to RN assessment. Opportunities warrant further studies because the total length of stay remains unchanged.

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BACKGROUND

A hospital's obstetric (OB) triage unit functions as an emergency department (ED) for pregnant women (Arora & Mercer, 2016; Evans, Watts, & Gratton, 2015; Kenyon et al., 2017). Similar to how an ED serves as the primary point of entry for patients entering the healthcare system, OB triage is the main point of entry for women seeking healthcare-related to their pregnancies (Arora & Mercer, 2016; Evans et al., 2015; Garrett et al., 2018).

The concept of triage came from the military, where workers in field hospitals used systematic protocols to evaluate and prioritize wounded soldiers quickly and thoroughly (American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists [ACOG], 2016). The OB triage unit and the ED both perform the same function of categorizing and prioritizing patients who arrive for emergent or urgent care before a specific evaluation and management. While triage activities in hospitals were typically associated with the ED, the concept of OB triage emerged in the early 1980s.

Before the 1980s, OB patients, regardless of gestation, were primarily seen in the ED. The creation of a separate OB triage unit allowed hospitals to evaluate pregnant women in an area adjacent to labor and delivery (LD). Separating OB patients from the ED was then enforced by the Emergency Medical Treatment and Active Labor Act (EMTALA) (Angelini & Howard, 2014).

In 1986, Congress enacted EMTALA to ensure access to emergency services regardless of a person's ability to pay. Section 1867 of the Social Security Act imposed specific obligations on Medicare-participating hospitals to provide a medical screening examination (MSE) when a request is made for an examination or treatment for an

emergency medical condition (EMC), including active labor (Center for Medicare and Medicaid Services [CMS], 2018). The purposes of an MSE are to determine whether an EMC exists, provide necessary stabilizing treatment, and stabilize the patient or arrange for proper transfer to another hospital if the benefits of a transfer outweigh the risks. The act mandates that only a qualified medical person (QMP) skilled in the evaluation of an OB patient can provide an MSE. The QMP includes Certified Nurse-Midwives (CNMs), Advanced Nurse Practitioners (ANP), LD nurses, and physicians (Angelini & Howard, 2014).

Typically, OB triage serves all pregnant women with 20-week or greater gestational age regardless of their healthcare treatment. Given that there is only one criterion (gestational age) for an MSE, the scope of an OB triage is broad and varied. The most common healthcare presentation is for an evaluation of labor at term but may include pregnancy-related complications such as preterm labor, signs and symptoms of preeclampsia, decreased fetal movement, premature rupture of membranes, vaginal bleeding, and acute abdominal pain. Acute and critical conditions, such as motor vehicle collision injury, abruptio placenta, or seizure, are rare, but they require immediate management (ACOG, 2016).

The triage unit's primary concern is to identify high acuity and life-threatening events. However, similar to an ED, the OB triage unit also serves as an outpatient, subacute healthcare provider where patients with benign or minor illnesses are often seen. Most patients are less acute, with 80% of emergency department patients discharged after an average stay of four hours and 76% of obstetric triage patients discharged after approximately two hours (Garrett et al., 2018; Kenyon et al., 2017). A wide range of

patient acuity, from life-threatening events to minor illnesses, often results in a sudden change in nursing workloads. Both acuity and workloads are ultimately attributable to an overcrowded triage (Arora & Mercer, 2016).

Problem Statement

In an OB triage, overcrowding can result in delayed services, which, in turn, can cause the triage area to be further crowded. Issues related to overcrowding include medical errors, increased length of stay (LOS), and decreased patient satisfaction (Arora & Mercer, 2016). Delayed services in an OB triage unit may also result in delayed clinical decisions that are necessary for safe delivery. Inadequate monitoring of the mother and fetus can result in an unnecessary emergency cesarean delivery or an uncontrolled delivery out of asepsis.

An ineffective triage that negatively influences throughput can also impact not only patients but also healthcare providers and organizations. While patients can experience delayed services, increased waiting time, or frustration from feeling ignored, nurses and physicians can feel overwhelmed. Also, inefficient bed utilization can result in negative financial consequences for the organization. Given limited healthcare resources and rising costs, there is mounting pressure to ensure that delivery of care is evidence-based and clinically effective as well as efficient and cost-effective.

The elements that constitute an OB triage's workflow can be illustrated using the economic concept of "supply and demand." Demand refers to how much consumers desire a product or service; supply represents how much of a product or service is available in a market. In a clinical setting, demand consists of the volume of patients and their needs, which are often quantified by a patient classification or an acuity system

(Arora & Mercer, 2016). Supply refers to the organization's capacity to meet a patient's clinical needs. Clinical capacity is a combination of available beds and competent healthcare providers, or staffing, for the necessary services. Staffing is set based on the quantified amount of demands, the number of patients, and their acuity score. In economics, supply and demand equally influence each other, but in a clinical setting, demand often overrules supply. In the context of an OB triage, a patient's needs and the number of competent staff are frequently mismatched as the variation of the acuity and volume of patients is wide and varied.

The OB triage unit at which this project took place also experienced the consequences of a mismatch between demand and the ability to provide services. Two possible factors that were related to this mismatch were a shortage of staffing and a lack of a standardized triage process. There were no permanently assigned triage RNs. Instead, the OB triage was staffed by LD RNs that were in rotation during each shift. While the OB triage always tried to maintain two RNs, this goal was often not met. When the pressing needs of patients in labor required an additional RN, one of the triage RNs was temporarily redeployed to assist the needs in LD. The triage process of a patient's screening, evaluation, and disposition was inevitably delayed until the nurse returned to OB triage. An inherent shortcoming of this staffing model was that a triage patient's needs became secondary to an LD patient's acute needs.

In previous studies, standardizing practices improved throughput efficiency (Arora & Mercer, 2016; Garrett et al., 2018). Additional benefits of standardized practice included reduced waiting time, increased the number of women examined within 15 minutes, improved patient satisfaction, enhanced communication among healthcare

providers, and improved patient safety (Arora & Mercer, 2016; Garrett et al., 2018; Keyon et al., 2017).

Many emergency departments have implemented a standardized triage practice process utilizing the Emergency Severity Index (ESI). The ED has also implemented an efficiency measure, i.e., the median time of ED arrival to ED departure, to achieve an optimal throughput (CMS, 2018; Gilboy et al., 2005; McHugh et al., 2012). However, metrics to assess an OB triage's throughput efficiency have not been established nor implemented.

While the improvement of throughput efficiency in an OB triage unit is a continuous goal, a lack of understanding of triage patient flow process is a barrier to patient care quality, as explored in studies (Arora & Mercer, 2016; Garrett et al., 2018; Keyon et al., 2017). The solution to inefficient workflow in an OB triage unit will not be discernible until the triage process is carefully examined and analyzed.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project is to optimize patient safety and throughput efficiency by implementing a standardized triage model in OB triage. This project aims to improve the accuracy of OB triage assessment and treatment, to improve the patient outcomes, and decrease the LOS in an OB triage.

Supporting Framework

Interdisciplinary stakeholders and influential factors impact the throughput process in an OB triage. To address the relationship between stakeholders as well as the influential factors, the Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services (PARiHS) was chosen as a guiding framework (Bonnell & Smith, 2014; Kitson, Harvey,

and McCormack (1998). Gaps, barriers, and areas requiring attention were identified through the PARiHS model's framework (Laycock et al., 2018; Stetler et al., 2011).

The PARiHS framework emphasizes knowledge translation, namely how to bring evidence to practice at the bedside level. The framework consists of three overarching elements: evidence, context, and facilitation. Figure 1 shows these three elements and their respective sub-elements.

Figure 1. The conceptual framework of the PARiHS model (Kitson et al., 1998).

Characteristics of the Evidence

The evidence in the PARiHS framework stems from several sources of knowledge and information. The three evidence bases are research, clinical experience, and patient preference (Kitson et al., 1998), and they correlate with the concept of

evidence-based practice (EBP), whose main features are hard scientific evidence, clinical expertise, and patient needs and choices (McKibbin, 1998).

Characteristics of the Context

The context is the environment or setting in which the proposed change is to be implemented (Kitson et al., 1998). Context is divided into three sub-elements: an understanding of the culture, the leadership, and the method of measurement for evaluation. It can be expanded to include the relevance of change, adequate resources for the change, and strategies with multi-disciplinary participation (Kitson et al., 1998).

Characteristics of the Facilitation

The PARiHS model defines facilitation as the process of “enabling people” to enculturate evidence in their clinical setting (Kitson et al., 1998). The process of “enabling people” means helping people to understand why the change is necessary and to change attitudes, habits, skills, and ways of thinking, and working with the new knowledge to achieve desired outcomes (Hauck et al., 2012; Rycroft-Malone, 2004). Several factors may influence how people respond to new knowledge, including motivation, values and beliefs, skills and knowledge, and time.

Facilitation requires interpersonal and group skills to help people. Unlike opinion leaders, facilitators have lateral and non-judgmental openness, supportiveness, approachability, reliability, and self-confidence (Kitson et al., 1998). The facilitator’s competency is divided into three levels—novice, experienced, and expert—based on his or her experiences and skills (Kitson et al., 1998; Kitson & Harvey, 2016;). Novice facilitators are more likely to lead the local implementation of a project while more experienced and expert facilitators implement projects with more complex barriers or

contextual factors. The more skilled the facilitation, the more likely the implementation will succeed.

Literature Review of the PARIHS Application

The literature offers a scholarly discussion on how the PARIHS framework translates evidence into practice. These publications illustrate the applicability of the framework, as well as the generalizability and sustainability of the projects' results.

Meijers et al. (2006) found that many healthcare organizations struggled in implementing new evidence into their clinical settings. The authors conducted a systematic review to identify contextual factors that are associated with research utilization in nursing. Out of 292 articles that met the initial search criteria, 10 studies were critically appraised. Six clusters of contextual factors were categorized and mapped in the PARIHS framework. Statistically significant contextual factors that were associated with research utilization in nursing included the role of the nurse, access to resources, organizational climate, support, time for research activities, and staff education (Meijers et al., 2006). This systematic review study illustrated that the PARIHS model is a useful conceptual framework that can address the complex nature of the clinical environment in which new knowledge is introduced.

Hauck et al. (2012) conducted a prospective, descriptive, comparative study. Using the PARIHS framework, the study assessed the impact of leadership facilitation strategies on nurses and the perception of organizational readiness in an acute care hospital. The authors identified an incongruence between leaders' knowledge and their behavior. A leader's strong understanding of EBP did not translate into facilitating its implementation at the bedside level. As a result, the ineffective leadership's facilitation

was perceived as a lack of support from the leaders. The authors suggested a formal education on methods to effectively facilitate the change as part of a leader's organizational preparation before implementing new strategies. The leadership curriculum included critical thinking, strategic visioning, inspiring and leading change, relationship building, emotional intelligence, managing complexity, and stewardship (Hauck et al., 2012). The authors also discussed the importance of contextualization when bringing EBP into a clinical setting. Change is more likely to be successful if key stakeholders are involved throughout the implementation process. The authors suggested that an EBP education should be offered to all key members of multi-disciplinary departments. The authors also emphasized the importance of an EBP-friendly environment, such as providing internal opportunities for scholarly discussions at various meetings and recognizing staff's contributions. The authors concluded that a contextualized implementation would improve the sustainability of the change (Hauck et al., 2012). This study demonstrated that the PARiHS framework was a useful framework that supports organizational change initiatives such as translating EBP into a clinical setting.

Gozdzik (2013) conducted a quality improvement (QI) project to develop partnerships among three separate clinical areas where high volumes of nephrology patients continuously move through. The goal of the study was to increase nurses' knowledge of best practices and, consequently, improve outcomes for the patients under their care by a seamless care transition among ED, intensive care unit, and in-patient nephrology unit. The author used the PARiHS model as a framework, concluded that the facilitator should assess the organizational context and the leader's readiness before

implementing new initiatives. The new initiatives must be aligned with the organizational context for sustaining a knowledge dissemination initiative (Goździk, 2013).

The PARiHS model illustrates the interplay of three core elements: the level of evidence, the context in which the evidence is to be implemented, and the effective method in which the implementation process is facilitated. The three elements are equally important; therefore, they must be balanced throughout the process of translating evidence into practice (Kitson et al., 1998).

Project Application of the PARiHS Framework

As a guiding framework of this project, the PARiHS assisted in identifying gaps and barriers as well as areas that required attention. In the following sections, a contextual application of each of the framework's elements was explored.

Figure 2. A conceptual framework for this project adapted from the PARiHS model (Kitson et al., 1998).

Evidence

This DNP project implemented an OB triage guideline (see Figure 2). To implement the guideline, several steps needed to occur, including a review of the literature to identify an evidence-based assessment tool that was designed for an OB triage setting, the attainment of stakeholder expertise and experiences, and the translation of evidence into the local context. Supportive evidence and research publications were utilized to assist stakeholders in understanding why the standardization of an OB triage process was necessary. Communication with stakeholders established a shared understanding.

The qualification for a competent triage RN was defined before implementing RN education. All qualified RNs participated in initial training and skills validation. Annual education and re-validation will be conducted to all qualified triage RNs.

Context

As a contextual change in this DNP project, a set of throughput metrics were identified and implemented to measure patient flow efficiency in an OB triage (see Figure 2). These metrics were become an ongoing dashboard to evaluate the sustainability of the changes introduced by this DNP project.

The triage nursing station was relocated to be adjacent to the patient's check-in window. This relocation allowed immediate RN's assessment before the triage patient was registered.

Facilitation

The facilitator leading this project was the department manager and DNP student. The facilitator helped achieve the project goal by enabling individuals and teams to

analyze, reflect, and modify their attitudes, behaviors, and work methods. The facilitator first secured the participation of stakeholders, including members of the nurse lead council, the unit-based council, the department director, the department educator, and the physicians and medical residents. The facilitator also interacted with key departments, including finance, risk management, and organizational excellence, to help support the changes.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The literature review for this project was conducted utilizing five databases: PubMed, Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health (CINAHL), Google Scholar, OneSearch, and Web of Science. Additionally, the table of contents of the Journal of Emergency Nursing, and Journal of Obstetric, Gynecologic, & Neonatal Nursing (JOGNN) were searched for relevant publications. The topics for the literature search included obstetric triage, standardization of practice, standardized triage tool, and patient outcomes. The search was limited to the English language, peer-reviewed articles, and the search dates were expanded from 1990 to April 2019 due to the limited number of articles related to the project topic.

Obstetric Triage

The OB triage is a specialized unit for obstetrical patients. Similar to how an ED serves as the primary point of entry for patients entering the healthcare system, the OB triage is the main point of entry for women seeking healthcare related to their pregnancies (Angelini & Howard, 2014; Arora & Mercer, 2016; Evans et al., 2015; Garrett et al., 2018). The purpose of OB triage is in many aspects identical to that of ED triage, such as rapidly assessing health problems, prioritizing and treating health problems, deploying healthcare providers and equipment, and arranging the disposition of patients (Mahlmeister & Van Mullem, 2000). Other functions of the OB triage include alleviating LD by serving as a patient holding area, performing selected obstetric procedures, and complying with regulatory law (Arora & Mercer, 2016; Evans, Watts, & Gratton, 2015; Kenyon et al., 2017).

Under EMTALA, OB triage is required to assess and treat pregnant women in active labor (Angelini & Howard, 2014; Gratton et al., 2016; Mahlmeister & Van Mullem, 2000). However, OB triage still lacks a standardized clinical and administrative protocol that is aligned with EMTALA (Angelini & Howard, 2014; Gratton et al., 2016; Mahlmeister & Van Mullem, 2000). Studies identified areas of concern, including a failure to perform a timely MSE, failure to make a proper disposition, failure to provide necessary advice to patients, and delay in or lack of inter-professional communication and documentation (Angelini & Howard, 2014; Gratton et al., 2016; Mahlmeister & Van Mullem, 2000). Unfortunately, there are limited studies regarding current OB triage practices. Gaps, barriers, and legal pitfalls that were identified in past studies still exist, and many hospitals have not updated their OB triage practices.

Although OB triage has many functions that are similar to ED, it also holds unique roles that are specific to OB (Angelini & Howard, 2014; AWHONN, 2019). Unlike an ED that “*transfers-out*” inpatients to other departments and hands-off care responsibility to care providers outside of ED, an OB triage “*transfers-in*” inpatients to LD unit, that is the only inpatient department for pregnant women (Arora & Mercer, 2016). LD and OB triage are one unit that shares the same clinical resources, such as available beds and healthcare providers. The care responsibility stays within the department (Arora & Mercer, 2016). The concept of transfer-in implies that triage is not merely a location but also a function of care. In 2015, AWHONN defined an OB triage as “the brief, systematic maternal and fetal assessment performed when a pregnant woman presents for care that allows for assignment of priority level for care and deployment of

personnel and equipment as indicated by the priority level based on the identified clinical needs” (AWHONN, 2014, p. 33).

Another unique aspect of OB care is that caring involves two or more lives in one person: a pregnant woman and a fetus or multiple fetuses (AWHONN, 2015). Each life has different parameters of assessment, diagnosis, treatment, and evaluation (AWHONN, 2015). Each life also might display separate healthcare needs at different time frames. The diversity and complexity of the patient's needs in an OB triage require refining and standardizing practices to achieve optimal outcomes (ACOG, 2016).

Standardization of Practice

Multiple studies have discussed the benefits of standardizing practices in an OB triage (Arora & Mercer, 2016; Garrett et al., 2018; Keyon et al., 2017). The benefits of standardizing practices include reducing variations in waiting time, improving throughput efficiency by increasing the number of women examined within 15 minutes, improving patient satisfaction, enhancing interprofessional communication, and improving patient safety. The subsequent benefits of standardizing practices in an OB triage that can, in turn, cross over to LD include the on-time case initiation for labor induction and cesarean birth as well as the reduction of unscheduled and uncontrolled deliveries (Bell, Bohannon, Porthouse, Thompson, & Vago, 2016).

Moreover, standardizing triage practices can positively impact the workflow in an OB triage (Arora & Mercer, 2014; Gratton et al., 2016). A retrospective descriptive study explored the mean patient volume in an OB triage in a mid-sized, tertiary-care, single, urban institution (Arora & Mercer, 2014). A total of 7,678 women visited its OB triage between June 1, 2013, and May 31, 2014. The mean volume of daily OB triage visits was

21 and fluctuated as much as six-fold (SD: 5.7). The patient volume between the least busy and busiest days ranged from 6 visits (28.6% of the mean volume) to 36 visits (171.4% of the mean volume). The volume variation among daily visits ranged from 3.8 to 17-fold on weekdays and from 4 to 11-fold on weekends (Arora & Mercer, 2014). Several studies recommended that the standardization of triage practice include a surge or capacity plan during a sudden increase of patient volume in the OB triage (ACOG, 2016; Arora & Mercer, 2014; Loper & Hom, 2000; Smithson, Twohey, Watts, & Gratton, 2016; Qualie, 2018).

A standardization of triage practices can also be a benefit in a low census setting (Angelini & LaFontaine, 2017). Data from a standardized practice will allow the tracking of patient complaints, acuity trends, and throughput processes to improve resource utilization (Angelini & LaFontaine, 2017).

Timeliness is a crucial factor for quality healthcare (Institute of Medicine, 2001). AWHONN has established that the benchmark for the time of arrival to an initial nursing assessment should be less than 10 minutes (AWHONN, 2014). Studies demonstrated that practice standardization also improved LOS in an OB triage (Smithson et al., 2016; Qualie, 2018). For example, in a study that analyzed pre- and post-implementation of standardized practice, the LOS decreased from 105 minutes to 98 minutes (Smithson et al., 2016). The intake time from a patient's arrival to an initial nursing assessment also improved pre- to post-implementation from 19 minutes to 10.4 minutes (Qualie, 2018).

Standardized Triage Tools

Emergency Department Triage Tools

Four ED triage tools are used worldwide: the Australasian Triage Scale, the Canadian Triage and Acuity Scale (CTAS), the Manchester Triage System (MTS), and the Emergency Severity Index (ESI) (Cicolo, Ayache, Nishi, Ciqueto Peres, & Cruz, 2017; Zachariasse et al., 2017). The goals of all ED tools are identical. They include the rapid assessment of healthcare needs, the assignment of priority, and the determination of maximum waiting time based on priority level (Cicolo et al., 2017; Zachariasse et al., 2017). Widely administered in the US, ESI uses an algorithm to provide a clinical stratification of patients into five groups, from level 1 (most urgent) to level 5 (least urgent) based on acuity and predicted resource needs. The maximum waiting time varies in levels. Level 1 patients require immediate care from a physician, whereas patients in level 2 through level 5 have stratified wait times of 10 minutes, 30 minutes, 60 minutes, and 120 minutes, respectively (Storm-Versloot, Ubbink, Kappelhof, & Luitse, 2011). However, ED triage tools have a limited application to an obstetrical context because the ED tool's acuity determinants do not reflect obstetrical health determinants (Angelini & LaFontaine, 2017; Gratton et al., 2016).

OB Triage Tools

Three OB triage tools have been identified in the literature: the Florida Hospital System (FHS) obstetric acuity tool, the Obstetrical Triage Acuity Scale (OTAS), and the Maternal Fetal Triage Index (MFTI) (AWHONN, 2019; Gratton et al., 2016; Paisley et al., 2011).

The FHS was the first published OB triage tool that recognized the need for a timely assessment and determination of patient acuity (Angelini & LaFontaine, 2017; Paisley et al., 2011). The primary goals of the FHS tool were to conduct an OB nurse initial assessment within 10 minutes of a patient's arrival and assign an acuity level to determine the time frame for an MSE. The five categories of acuity and the time frame for MSE were defined as 1) Immediate—immediate (red), 2) Urgent—within 15 minutes (purple), 3) Semi urgent—within 30 minutes (yellow), 4) Less urgent—within 60 minutes (green), and 5) Procedure/testing—less than or equal to 120 minutes (gray). This tool, however, was intended to be used within one healthcare system (FHS) and has not been studied for inter-rater reliability and content validity (Angelini & LaFontaine, 2017; Paisley et al., 2011).

The OTAS was based on the Canadian Triage Assessment Scale, the first OB triage acuity tool with a demonstrated inter-rater reliability and content validity (Angelini & LaFontaine, 2017; Paisley et al., 2011). Both the FHS and the OTAS are color-coded five-category acuity tools with identical time frames for an initial RN assessment and an MSE (Gratton et al., 2016; Paisley et al., 2011). The five categories of the OTAS acuity and the time frame for MSE included 1) Resuscitative—immediate (red), 2) Emergent—within 15 minutes (orange), 3) Urgent—within 30 minutes (yellow), 4) Less urgent—within 60 minutes (green), and 5) Non-urgent—less than or equal to 120 minutes (blue). Contrary to the FHS, the OTAS defined a specific timeframe for an RN's reassessment that decreases with decreased acuity. For example, while continuous monitoring is required for patients at level 1, the frequency of RN assessment decreased to 15 minutes

for patients at levels 2 and 3, every 30 minutes for level 4 patients, and every 60 minutes for level 5 patients.

Developed in the U.S., the MFTI is the first OB triage tool designed for multidisciplinary use and demonstrated content validity and inter-rater reliability (Killion, 2016; Ruhl et al., 2015). The tool uses a five-tiered approach for categorizing acuity: “Priority 1—stat” requires immediate lifesaving intervention for a woman or her fetus; “Priority 2—urgent” covers severe pain not related to contractions, high-risk clinical condition, or the need for transfer to a higher level of care; “Priority 3—prompt” includes women at or over 34-week gestation in active labor; “Priority 4—non-urgent” includes women at term gestation in early labor; and “Priority 5—scheduled or requesting a service” includes women presenting for scheduled procedures or routine prenatal care (Ruhl et al., 2015).

The MFTI recommends the benchmark time for an initial nursing assessment to be less than 10 minutes (AWHONN, 2014). Unlike the FHS and OTAS, the tool does not identify other essential benchmarks such as a timeframe for an MSE and the frequency of an RN’s reassessments while waiting for an MSE (Angelini & LaFontaine, 2017; Ruhl et al., 2015). The MFTI, instead, suggests an institutional decision for acceptable time parameters (Angelini & LaFontaine, 2017; Ruhl et al., 2015).

For the successful implementation of a standardized triage tool, the competence of the bedside clinician was an influencing factor (Mahlmester & Mullem, 2000; Quaile, 2018). Studies identified that the accuracy of the acuity relied solely on the skill of the clinicians. The validation of the clinicians’ competence and compliance with a tool

utilization was essential to successfully change an organization's practice (Mahlmester & Mullem, 2000; Quaile, 2018).

Patient Outcomes

Although the OB triage's primary focus is to manage high acuity and life-threatening events, it also serves as an outpatient, subacute healthcare provider for many people with benign or minor illnesses (Garret et al., 2018; Matteson, Witzgen, Lafontaine, & Phipps, 2008). In a prospective study of 287 pregnant women who came to an OB triage for non-emergent reasons, 36% of the women believed they had an actual emergency, 42% were sent by a physician, and 21% presented because they had no other means but OB triage to report their health care needs (Matteson et al., 2008). Most of these patients were of lower acuity, with 76% of OB triage patients discharged after approximately two hours (Garrett et al., 2018; Kenyon et al., 2017).

A prospective observational cohort study with pregnant women (37 to 41 weeks of gestation) examined Cesarean delivery rates and the perinatal composite outcome rates between a group of 3,949 women who were sent home with a diagnosis of false labor and a group of 2,592 women who were admitted in spontaneous early labor (Nelson, McIntire, & Leveno, 2017). The results showed no significant difference in all study variables, including the perinatal composite outcome indicators, such as respiratory insufficiency, intraventricular hemorrhage, culture-proven sepsis, Apgar score three or less at five minutes, phototherapy, and perinatal death (Nelson et al., 2017).

Although the women who were discharged from the OB triage reported that they were satisfied with the services, nearly half of the pregnant women (41%) said that they did not want to be discharged (Evans et al., 2015; Hoesk, Faucher, Lankfor, & Alexander,

2014). They felt they were in too much pain to go home or were concerned because they lived too far from the hospital (Hoesk et al., 2014). The authors discussed several clinical methods to help assuage patient perceptions and reduce their anxiety. In an OB triage, a provider's holistic, genuine, caring, and attentive approach can build trust in his or her clinical decision, including the discharge of patients. Effective communication, such as clear, detailed, and specific written instructions about early labor and comfort measures, was also associated with reducing women's anxiety (Evans et al., 2015; Hoesk et al., 2014).

A systematic review of 33 studies examined the use of triage concepts in obstetrics over 15 years, from 1998 to 2013, and recommended a set of best practice implications for an OB triage (Angelini & Howard, 2014). The recommendations included the use of an acuity scale designed for an OB triage, the standardization of assessment, adequate staffing, a measurement of patient flow, fast-tracking non-emergent obstetric conditions, the development of protocols that are aligned with EMTALA, identification of liability pitfalls, the establishment of a collaborative interprofessional practice model, ongoing simulation drills, and quality improvement that tracks acuity, LOS, and patient satisfaction (Angelini & Howard, 2014).

Even though each pregnant woman may present with unique healthcare needs, the literature recommends standardized and prioritized care. Standardized terminologies and prioritized assessments will reduce practice variations, improve the quality and safety of patient care, and improve patient's experience in OB triage.

METHODS

This chapter describes procedures that were used to achieve the purpose of this project, including the setting, samples, procedure, and data collection. The purpose of this project was to implement a standardized OB triage intake model in an OB triage unit. By standardizing the intake process in an OB triage unit, the aim of this project was to improve the accuracy and timeliness of OB triage care. Subsequently, the accurate and timely intake were to impact patient outcomes and LOS. The PARiHS model guided the implementation process, and its three elements were incorporated and contextualized in the processes.

Ethical Considerations

The facility administrator provided a letter of support (see Appendix A). An Institutional Review Board (IRB) application process was completed with California State University, Los Angeles, and the organization at which this project was conducted (see Appendix B and C).

This project involved minimal risk to project participants. The project abided by all requirements of confidentiality under the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act. Participants were not individually identified. Participants' confidentiality was protected by assigning sequential code numbers that were unrelated to their identifiable personal information. The data collection records were securely stored on the author's password secured computer. The project's results were only reported in aggregated data.

Setting

The setting for this DNP project was 353-bed acute care, a non-profit, faith-based hospital located in the greater Los Angeles metropolitan area. The hospital is a member of a healthcare system that consists of 22 affiliated acute care hospitals located throughout the Western United States. This facility provided a full range of inpatient, outpatient, emergency, and diagnostic services.

Obstetric services at the hospital include caring for low- to high-risk OB patients, maternal-fetal medicine, and perinatology. The LD department is located on the third floor of the specialty care tower. The LD consisted of 10 private labor and delivery rooms, three operation rooms, and four recovery bays. Approximately 3,600 newborns are delivered annually. The OB triage, which was adjacent to LD, consisted of five bays and three private holding rooms. The OB triage has approximately 7,500 visits a year.

Sample

This project included all LD RNs who had a minimum of 2 years of direct patient care experience in LD. This project also included a review of medical records of pregnant women who visited the OB triage in two–6 weeks' time frames: November 24, 2018, through January 4, 2019, and November 24, 2019, through January 4, 2020.

Procedures

Review of Literature

The OB triage lacked a standardized clinical and administrative protocol that is aligned with EMTALA (Angelini & Howard, 2014; Gratton et al., 2016; Mahlmeister & Van Mullem, 2000). Studies identified areas of concern, including a failure to perform a timely MSE, failure to make a proper disposition, failure to provide necessary advice to

patients, and delay in or lack of inter-professional communication and documentation (Angelini & Howard, 2014; Gratton et al., 2016; Mahlmeister & Van Mullem, 2000). A systematic review suggested several recommendations to improve OB triage, such as the use of an acuity scale designed for OB triage, standardization of assessment, development of protocols that are aligned with EMTALA, and establishment of a collaborative interprofessional practice model (Angelini & Howard, 2014).

Selection a Triage Guideline

The AWHONN's MFTI was selected as the OB triage tool for this project. The MFTI was the most widely adopted and implemented OB triage tool in the U.S. (Ruhl et al., 2015a; Ruhl et al., 2015b). The MFTI was a five-level acuity-based OB triage tool for RN's initial assessment, changed the order in which MSE to be performed, from traditional first-come, first-serve to acuity-based. The tool also provided a standardized intake process to minimize practice variations among the triage RNs. This algorithm has demonstrated content validity (0.95) and inter-rater reliability (0.65) (Ruhl et al., 2015a; Ruhl et al., 2015b). In addition to the MFTI, a flow chart of the OB triage workflow was developed as a staff reference (see Appendix D).

Change of the Intake Workflow

The new intake process required RNs to immediately conduct an MFTI assessment before the triage patient was registered. To provide an immediate RN assessment, the triage nursing station was relocated to be adjacent to the patient's check-in window. Patients with priority levels of 1 or 2 were bedded for an immediate MSE, whereas the priority levels of 3, 4, and 5 were considered safe to return to the waiting room until they were called in for an MSE.

Education and Validation of RN Competency

The project leader and the OB educator developed the curriculum for RN education. The curriculum consisted of five online modules, including EMTALA law and OB service, MFTI algorithm, MFTI poster, OB triage workflow, and initial triage form. The modules were assigned to RNs via HealthStream e-learning system. The expected time to complete all modules was 60 minutes. A scenario-based e-test was used to validate nurses' understanding of the contents of the online modules. A test score of 100 % was required to pass the test. Retaking the test was allowed until scoring 100%.

The OB educator was assigned to provide the RN competency validation, reinforcing the curriculum content that RNs had already reviewed through the e-training modules. This in-person validation session was conducted either by a group or individual education sessions.

Facilitation of the Implementation

The project leader met with leading stakeholders, including members of Nurse Lead and Unit-Based Councils, the OB nurse director, and the OB physicians, and shared the implementation plan. The MFTI workflow was introduced to the admitting department as it impacted the patient registration process.

The department manager (the author of the project), the supervisor, and the OB educator rounded on the triage RNs and facilitated the implementation. Daily debriefing was conducted with the OB triage staff to facilitate the practice change.

Data Collection

Several data sets were collected for this project. First, data were collected on the number of RNs and the years of RNs' LD experience. Data also included the number of completions of e-training and skills validation. The data were stratified by shift.

Second, 150 available medical records, from November 24, 2019, to January 4, 2020, were reviewed for the accuracy of MFTI classification and intervention. Those with an inaccurate MFTI score were further evaluated to determine specifics of the case and identify patterns and trends. These data were stratified by shift.

The third data set was for LOS. A total of 300 medical records were reviewed to assess total LOS as well as the time for RN's initial MFTI assessment. Of 300 medical records, 150 records were baseline data from November 24, 2018, to January 4, 2019, and the next 150 records were post-implementation data from November 24, 2019, to January 4, 2020. The inclusion criteria for this data set were all pregnant women who presented to the OB triage then discharged home undelivered. The exclusion criteria were pregnant women who were admitted, transferred to another facility, eloped, left without being seen, or left against medical advice. The median LOS was used rather than the average mean LOS because the mean can be skewed by a few extreme outliers (Lee, Fung, & Fu, 2003).

The last data set assessed patient outcomes. This data set included *all* patients who visited the OB triage during the data collection periods. Data collection consisted of the number of deliveries, the number of improper discharges, the number of precipitous deliveries, and the deliveries out of sepsis. Maternal outcomes were assessed by the types of deliveries and the incidence of postpartum hemorrhage. Newborn outcomes were by the Apgar score at five minutes of birth.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to describe the number of participating RNs, and the number of completions of e-training and skills validation. Descriptive statistics analyzed the total number and percentage of accurate and inaccurate triage assessments. The status of over-triage and under-triage were described in descriptive statistics. Descriptive statistics were also used to analyze LOS as well as patient outcomes. Maternal statistics included the number and types of deliveries as well as complications. Newborn statistics included Apgar score at five minutes.

RESULTS

The purpose of this DNP project was to optimize patient safety and throughput efficiency by implementing a standardized triage model in an OB triage. The aims of this project were to improve the accuracy of OB triage assessment and treatment, to improve patient outcomes, and decrease the LOS in an OB triage. The results section discusses the findings and analysis of this project.

Participating RNs

Figure 3. Distribution of participating RNs stratified by shifts.

Figure 3 illustrates the distribution of participating RNs by shifts; day and night shifts. Compared to 81% of day shift RNs ($n = 29$), only 44% of night RNs ($n = 14$) had two or more years of LD experience, thus, included in the project. All 43 participating

RNs completed all five-online e-training modules via HealthStream. All of the RNs scored the passing grade on the validation test.

The MFTI went live on October 15, 2019, and RNs' competency validation process also began. Twenty-six out of 43 participating RNs (60%) completed the competency validation by October 31, 2019. Out of 26 RNs who completed the validation, 23 RNs (88.5%) were day shift, and 3 RNs (11.5%) were night shift. While the ideal validation completion date was October 31, 2019, an unforeseen barrier occurred. The author of the project and the OB educator who planned to lead the competency validation process were re-assigned to other projects by the organization. The MFTI validation dates had to be rescheduled and conducted sporadically over several weeks until all participating RNs completed the validation in December 2019.

Accuracy of RN Assessment

Figure 4. The number of RN assessment and assessment accuracy.

The data to examine the accuracy of the RN assessment was collected from 150 available OB patients' records. Of the 150 records, approximately two-thirds of the patients were triaged by day shift ($n = 95$, 63.3%), and the rest of the patients were triaged by night shift ($n = 55$, 36.7%). This proportion of samples per shift was similar to the proportion of the average patient volumes per shift.

Of the 150 records reviewed, 128 patients (85.3 %) were triaged accurately following the MFTI algorithm. Figure 4 displays the proportion of the number of patients whose MFTI assessments were accurate, as well as whose assessments were inaccurate.

Figure 5. The number of RN assessment and accuracy rate by shift.

Figure 5 illustrates the rates of accurate MFTI assessment per shift by day and night shifts. Within the respective shift, the night shift demonstrated a higher accuracy rate (91%) than that of the day shift (82%).

Figure 6. Distribution of MFTI priority levels.

Figure 6 depicts the breakdown of the priority levels as accurate, over-triaged, or under-triaged. The bar graph appears to be similar to a bell curve. One patient was prioritized as level 1. Most of the patients ($n = 127$, 84.7%) fell in the levels of 2, 3, or 4, and the numbers of patients in each level were 40, 39, 48, respectively.

A total of 22 patients were mistriaged. The highest incidence of inaccurate assessment was found in the group of level 2 patients. Of the group in level 2, 10 patients

were under-triaged, and one patient was over-triaged. These 11 patients in level 2 were accountable for 50% of the total 22 mistriaged incidences.

Table 1

Distribution of Inaccurate RN Assessment per Shift

Over- or under-triaged	<i>n</i>	%
Over-triaged (<i>n</i> = 9, 40.9%)		
Day Shift	6	66.7%
Night Shift	3	33.3%
Under-triaged (<i>n</i> = 13, 59.1%)		
Day Shift	11	84.6%
Night Shift	2	15.4%

Among 22 patients who were inaccurately triaged, more than half of the patients (*n* = 13, 59.1%) were under-triaged (see Table 1). The incidence of under-triage assessment was higher in day shift (*n* = 11, 84.6%) than night shift (*n* = 2, 15.4%).

Table 2

Breakdown of Priority Levels of the Under-triaged Patients

MFTI Levels Assigned	MFTI Levels Corrected	<i>n</i>	%
3	2	6	46.2%
4	2	4	30.8%
	3	2	15.4%
5	4	1	7.7%

The sum of % may not be 100% due to a roundup.

Table 2 shows the priority level breakdown of the patients who were under-triaged. Ten (76.9 %) out of 13 patients were under-triaged at level 3 (*n* = 6, 46.1%) or level 4 (*n* = 4, 30.8%) instead of correct level of 2. Two patients of level 3 were under-triaged to level 4. One patient of level 3 was three mistriaged to level 4.

Table 3

Chief Complaints of the Under-triaged Patients

Chief Complaints	Number of Patients (%)
Less than 34 Weeks Gestation with Signs of Uterine Contractions, Vaginal Bleedings, or Ruptured Membranes	7 (53.8%)
Decreased Fetal Movement	3 (23.1%)
Recent Trauma including Fall, Motor Vehicle Accident	3 (23.1%)

The 13 under-triaged patients presented one of the three commonly seen healthcare concerns in an OB triage unit. These three concerns were recent trauma, a complaint of decreased fetal movement, and less than 34 weeks of gestation with complaints of, or detectable, uterine contractions. Table 3 shows the distribution of the patients per each chief complaint. More than half of the under-triaged assessments ($n = 7$, 53.8%) were found in the group of patients whose primary reason to visit the triage was premature labor signs and symptoms before 34 weeks of gestational age.

Length of Stay

For a comparative analysis of LOS, two sets of 150 patients' records were reviewed. The exclusion criteria were pregnant women who were admitted to LD, transferred out to other departments or other hospitals, had eloped, left without being seen, or left against medical advice. Out of the 150 baseline data, 70 records were excluded, and out of 150 post-implementation data, 75 records were excluded.

Table 4

LOS of the Patients Who Were Discharged Home

Subsets of LOS	2018 (<i>n</i> = 80)	2019 (<i>n</i> = 75)	Goal Times*
Time to Initial RN Assessment	22 min	5 min	10 min (Range: 5-15 min)
Arrival to Departure	121 min	122 min	205 min (Range: 70-253 min)

All minutes (min) are Median Time; *Goal times include all types of dispositions.

Time to initial assessment showed a significant reduction in waiting time from 22 minutes to 5 minutes after the MFTI tool was implemented. The average LOS, from arrival to departure, was unchanged from 121 minutes from 122 minutes (see Table 4).

Patient Outcomes

Safe Discharge

Of the 150 post-implementation records, half of the patients were discharged home (*n* = 75, 50%), and another half of the patients were admitted (*n* = 75, 50%). Of those 75 patients who were discharged home, 60 patients were accurately triaged per the MFTI algorithm, and 15 patients were inaccurately triaged, either over-triaged (*n* = 5) or under-triaged (*n* = 10).

Of the 75 patients who were discharged home, no patient returned to the OB triage because of an inappropriate discharge, such as errors in diagnosis, prognosis, lack of treatment in OB triage, or errors in the discharge plan. The shortest unplanned return to the OB triage was a patient who came back in 4 hours to the OB triage with symptoms of active labor. The EMR review on the previous visit, however, confirmed that her discharge was appropriate then.

Delivery Outcomes

Table 5

Frequency Table of Maternal and Newborn Outcomes

Variables	2018 <i>n</i> = 555	2019 <i>n</i> = 378
Maternal Outcomes		
Types of Delivery		
Vaginal Delivery	435 (78.4%)	278 (73.5%)
Primary C-Section	54 (9.7%)	43 (11.4%)
Repeat C-Section	66 (11.9%)	57 (15.1%)
Postpartum Hemorrhage	3 (0.5%)	6 (1.5%)
Newborn Outcomes		
Apgar Score at 5 min		
7 or Greater	545 (98.2%)	368 (97.4%)
Less than 7	10 (1.8%)	10 (2.6%)

Table 5 is a summary of the patient outcomes on all patients who delivered during the data collection period. A total of 933 delivery outcomes was reviewed. A significant decrease in delivery volumes was noted from 2018 to 2019. The outcomes of the variables were relatively unchanged.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this project was to optimize patient safety and throughput efficiency by implementing a standardized triage model in an OB triage. The aims of this project were to improve the accuracy of OB triage assessment and treatment, to improve the patient outcomes, and decrease the LOS in an OB triage.

Accuracy of RN Assessment

Of the 150 records reviewed, 85.3 % ($n = 128$) were triaged accurately following the MFTI algorithm. Although limited studies were available, the result of 85.3 % MFTI accuracy rate within a month of implementation was promising. One study categorized a 72.9% accuracy rate as a successful implementation (Ruhl et al., 2015b) while another had plateaued at near 90% accuracy after an MFTI implementation (Smithson et al., 2013).

Although our accuracy rate was considered acceptable, a continuous effort to achieve 100% accuracy should continue. One recent study reported a rapid improvement from 50% to 100% accuracy rate within three months when additional training was provided through case study discussions in group meetings and individual coaching (Murray & Danford, 2019). Other suggestions for improvement of the MFTI accuracy include ongoing reinforcement to experienced nurses (who may still rely on their own informal triaging assessments) and structured training of midlevel and junior nurses who are orienting to OB triage (Smithson et al., 2013). Ongoing education on the principles and care benefits of triaging, auditing of compliance, and setting targets are also found to be vital to the successful implementation of MFTI (Smithson et al., 2013).

Over- or under-triage can impact timely treatment. Especially, closer attention must be given to under-triaged patients as it can cause delayed treatment or inaccurately influence disposition of the patient. There were 13 under-triaged patients whose intake was possibly managed less urgently. Ten (76.9 %) out of 13 patients were under-triaged to level 3 ($n = 6$, 46.1%) or level 4 ($n = 4$, 30.8%) instead of correct level of 2. Two patients (15.4%) in level 3 were under-triaged to level 4. One patient (7.7%) whose correct level was four was mistriaged to level 5. A study with 69 ED RNs that triaged 2,069 cases examined the accuracy of the ESI and the rates of over- or under-triage (Hinson et al., 2018). This study reported that nearly one in five patients was under- or over-triaged. The most inaccurate initial ESI assessment occurred at the mid-level of 3. The patients with level 3 were triaged with lower acuity levels of 4 and 5. The results of this project and the study by Hinson et al. (2018) suggested that a need for greater emphasis and improvement on MFTI accuracy among the mid-level priorities.

In this project, three chief complaints were identified as independent predictors of under-triage, i.e., less than 34 weeks' gestation with signs of labor ($n = 7$, 53.8%), decreased fetal movement ($n = 3$, 23.1%), and recent trauma including fall, motor vehicle accident ($n = 3$, 23.1%). While no OB studies were available to compare with these findings, the result is alarming in that these health concerns are among the most commonly seen in OB triage (ACOG, 2016). The incidence rate of preterm labor in the U.S. was 9.8% in 2016. Of the preterm deliveries of 24-33 weeks' gestation, in addition to neonatal complications due to preterm births, 8.6% of mothers experienced serious maternal complications (Reddy et al., 2015). Maternal perception of decreased fetal movement is associated with adverse pregnancy and birth outcomes, affecting up to 15%

of pregnancies (Winje et al., 2016). Fall during pregnancy is not uncommon (Baker & Dupree, 2015). Up to 30 % of pregnant women experience one or more falls. Most falls result in no or minor injuries yet, in some cases, can be harmful to the mother and or baby.

Length of Stay

Timeliness is a crucial factor for quality healthcare (Institute of Medicine, 2001). The project's result showed that a decrease in the average median time of an RN's initial MFTI assessment from 22 minutes to 5 minutes, representing a 77% decrease. This result met the 10-minute benchmark for the time of an initial nursing assessment (AWHONN, 2014) and was consistent with prior studies. Murray and Danford (2019) reported that the time from a patient's arrival to the MFTI priority index assignment was reduced from 21.6 minutes to 6.3 minutes with MFTI implementation. Quaile (2018) also found a decrease in an RN's initial assessment times from 19 minutes to 10.4 minutes, Richter, Brennan & Sogn's (2019) reported that the mean wait time was reduced by 5.7 minutes as a result of MFTI implementation.

This decrease, however, did not result in a reduction of total LOS from arrival to departure. The average total LOS was unchanged from a baseline of 121 minutes to 122 minutes, post implementing the MFTI algorithm. Although no OB studies were available to compare with this result in the limited OB triage literature, Smithson et al. (2016) reported that total LOS was reduced from 105 minutes to 98 minutes when the standardized 5-category OTAS and a fast track service were implemented together. The authors reported that a fast-track for lower acuity patients (OTAS 4 and 5) reduced total

LOS to 73 minutes ($p = 005$), and the overall LOS decreased to 98 minutes (6.9% reduction; $p < .001$).

Several studies reported benefits of a fast-track model in ED (Celona et al., 2018; Chrusciel et al., 2019; Fitzgerald, Pelletier, & Reznick, 2017; Hwang, Lipman, & Kane, 2015). The fast track refers to a designated area and service where lower acuity ED patients are rapidly seen (Hwang et al., 2015). A fast track showed improved timeliness of care, such as reducing door-to-provider time, treat and release time, and the number of patients who left without being seen (Celona et al., 2018; Chrusciel et al., 2019; Fitzgerald et al., 2017). An ED fast track also showed a significant improvement in patient satisfaction score, that CMS drives, that could impact the amount of CMS funded reimbursement dollars (Hwang et al., 2015). Often, such fast track in ED is managed by nurse practitioners (Celona et al., 2018); therefore, opportunities warrant further studies to adopt the nurse-managed fast track model in the OB triage unit.

Factors that could have impacted the total LOS were not collected nor investigated during this project and will be analyzed in the second phase of data collection and analysis. This next phase of data collection and analysis will include the time from arrival to the time of an MSE, from the time of an MSE to the time of decision for disposition, and from the time of decision for disposition to the time of departure from OB triage. Possible factors that may impact the OB triage workflow were explored in the OB Triage Patient Flow Process map (see Appendix D).

There was a significant volume drop in deliveries from the baseline data of 555 to post-implementation of 378 (31.9% decrease). Exploring the causes of the delivery volume change is out of the scope of this project. Zocco, Williams, Longobucco, &

Bernstein et al. (2007) examined variables involved in workflow efficiency in OB triage. Their study identified that a wide range of LOS in OB triage exists. The average LOS of preterm premature rupture of the membrane was 73.1 minutes, while that of rule-out preeclampsia was 204.4 minutes (Zocco et al., 2007). Besides, the result of the study suggested that triage LOS was strongly dependent on the provider's availability to assess, triage, and discharge patients (Zocco et al., 2007).

Patient Outcomes

The project findings reported that no unnecessary emergency cesarean delivery or an uncontrolled delivery out of asepsis occurred during the data collection period. There were also no adverse patient outcomes nor improper patient discharges.

Limitations

There are limitations to the generalizability of this project. The findings may not be generalizable because the project was conducted in a single OB triage unit. There were time constraints for the project, as the data collection period was limited to 6 weeks. Auditing was restricted to 150 available records; this created potential sampling bias in that the sample may not have represented the entire population. The element of membership bias was also present because the project leader who collected and analyzed the data was familiar with the goals of the project. The DNP author, who was also the project leader, was highly involved in the facilitation of the implementation of the MFTI tool. Finally, competing priorities in the organization delayed the validation process over a more extended time. To what extent the delayed validation process impacted the result of the accuracy of the MFTI assessment is unknown.

Recommendations for Future Research

Although the project enhanced patient safety, results showed no changes in the average LOS from arrival to departure, from a baseline of 121 minutes to 122 minutes. Further study can focus on identifying contributing factors of delays in OB triage, such as the distribution of various diagnoses, acuity of patients in the triage as well as in labor and delivery, provider's availability, patient volumes, and delivery volumes. The subsets of LOS that can be used in future studies include the time from arrival to the time of an MSE, from the time of an MSE to the time of decision for disposition, and from the time of decision for disposition to the time of departure from OB triage. Future studies can also include implementing ED's fast track model in OB triage for lower acuity pregnant women.

SUMMARY

A hospital's OB triage unit functions as an emergency department for pregnant women (Arora & Mercer, 2016; Evans, Watts, & Gratton, 2015; Kenyon et al., 2017). It is the main point of entry for women seeking healthcare-related to their pregnancies (Arora & Mercer, 2016; Evans et al., 2015; Garrett et al., 2018). The triage unit's primary function is to identify high acuity and life-threatening events promptly. However, the triage unit often faces overcrowdedness due to many contributing factors that negatively impact the patient's length of stay.

The purpose of this DNP project was to optimize patient safety and throughput efficiency by implementing a standardized triage model in an OB triage. Safety was enhanced, as demonstrated by a high rate of accuracy in triage acuity and the time to RN assessment. Opportunities remain because the total length of stay remained unchanged.

Incremental assessments and evaluations will continue for ongoing improvement beyond the scope of this project.

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APPENDIX A
FACILITY LETTER OF SUPPORT

Support Letter

June 19, 2019

To: California State University, DNP Consortium

This letter documents my strong support for the proposed study *Developing and Implementing a Standardized Triage Model in OB Triage* by Eun (Kay) Yang, the nurse leading this quality improvement project. The project's purpose reflects the Adventist Health White Memorial's commitment for clinical excellence and continuous improvement by identifying a clinical opportunity or gap, and utilizing evidence-based guidelines to meet the clinical need. Adoption of the guidelines will ensure that our OB triage patients are managed more safely, effectively and efficiently.

I lend my full support for this project for Eun (Kay)'s Doctor of Nursing Practice project at California State University.

Sincerely,

Patricia Stone, RN, MSN

Vice President / Patient Care Executive
Adventist Health White Memorial
1720 Cesar E. Chavez Avenue
Los Angeles, CA 90033
Office: (323) 265-5087
Email: stonep1@ah.org

www.whitememorial.com

APPENDIX B
IRB APPROVAL FROM CSU, LA

Office Memorandum

DATE: October 8, 2019

TO: Elizabeth Winokur

FROM: Elia Amaro

PROJECT TITLE: [1462490-1] Developing and Implementing a Standardized Triage Model in OB Triage

REFERENCE #: 19-24X

SUBMISSION TYPE: New Project

ACTION: DETERMINATION OF EXEMPT STATUS

DECISION DATE: October 8, 2019

REVIEW CATEGORY: Exemption category # 2(iii)

Thank you for your submission of New Project materials for this project. The California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB has determined that this project is EXEMPT FROM IRB REVIEW according to federal regulations.

We will retain a copy of this correspondence within our records.

IF ANY CHANGES ARE MADE TO THE METHODS AND PROCEDURES DESCRIBED IN THIS PROTOCOL, YOU MUST SUBMIT A MODIFICATION APPLICATION SO THAT THE PROJECT MAY BE RE-EVALUATED FOR EXEMPTION FROM IRB REVIEW.

For any inquiries about this project, please use the Send Project Mail option on IRBNet to contact Elia Amaro. **It allows us to keep all correspondence related to this project in one place, rather than scattered between IRBNet and emails.**

This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB's records.

APPENDIX C

IRB APPROVAL FROM FACILITY

Memo

To: Eun (Kay) Yang, MS, RN
From: Michael Jordan, MSN, MBA
Director, Integrated Research
Date: April 16, 2019
Title: "Developing and Implementing a Standardized Triage Model in OB Triage"

Dear Ms. Yang

This memo confirms that I grant you permission to access and use patient data from our facility for your DNP project. The purpose of this project is to develop and implement a standardized triage model in OB Triage.

It is understood that the clinical data will be used only for the purpose of your project. Forms used during data collection will be housed in a locked file cabinet at your residence during the study, and when data has been entered into database, will be destroyed. The data will be de-identified and result will be reported in an aggregate form. Additionally, it is understood that this facility will be referred to only as "a tertiary acute care hospital in Los Angeles County". It will remain an anonymous institution in your project.

Best wishes with your degree program and your research!

Sincerely,

I am happy to support your project and wish you the best!

Michael Jordan, MSN, MBA
Director, Integrated Research
Adventist Health White Memorial

APPENDIX D

OB TRIAGE PATIENT FLOW PROCESS

APPENDIX E

PERMISSION TO USE PARIHS MODEL

Eun Yang <yangek@csu.fullerton.edu>

May 10, 2019, 10:47
PM

to gillian.harvey

Dear Dr. Harvey,

I am a DNP student at California State University in the U.S. and currently working on my DNP project. I would like your permission to use the PARIHS model and corresponding figure in the project. Applying the PARIHS in my practice change project brought the multi-faceted nature of each construct and the multi-layered process of the system to life. Thank you in advance for your kind consideration.

Sincerely,

Eun Yang, RN

Gillian Harvey <[REDACTED]>

May 12, 2019, 5:02
PM

to me

Dear Eun – lovely to hear from you and that you have found the PARIHS model helpful in your research.

Can you clarify which figure you are planning to use then I can check whether I have the appropriate copyright permissions to grant access. Could you send me a return email with a copy of the figure you are referring to?

Many thanks

Gill

Gill Harvey| Professorial Research Fellow

Adelaide Nursing School| Adelaide Health & Medical Sciences Building, Level 6|
Corner North Terrace & George Street| The University of Adelaide| SA 5005
Australia|

Tel: +61 8 8313 0267

Email: [REDACTED]

<http://health.adelaide.edu.au/nursing/> <https://www.facebook.com/uonanursing>

IMPORTANT: This message may contain confidential or legally privileged information. If you think it was sent to you by mistake, please delete all copies and advise the sender. For the purposes of the SPAM Act 2003, this email is authorised by The University of Adelaide.

Think green: read on the screen.

CRICOS Provider Number 00123M

Eun Yang <yangek@csu.fullerton.edu>

May 12, 2019, 8:58
PM

to Gillian

Dr. Harvey,

I was referring to the original PARIHS model from 1998. [Kitson, A., Harvey, G., & McCormack, B. (1998). Enabling the implementation of evidence based practice: A conceptual framework. *Quality in Health Care*, 7(3), 149-58.]

Although the figure is not an exact figure shown in the article, I think I need permission to use the concept of the three overarching elements of the model. Please see below.

Thank you!

Gillian Harvey <[REDACTED]>

May 12, 2019, 11:26
PM

to me

Hi Eun – yes it is fine to use the figure and say it is adapted from Kitson et al. (1998) etc.
With best wishes

Eun Yang <yangek@csu.fullerton.edu>

May 12, 2019, 11:45
PM

to Gillian

Thank you!